

(iii) Mono aza trimethin cyanines (I, X = N, Y and Z = CH) were prepared by heating the 2-amino quaternary salt with acetanilido vinyl derivatives of different 2-methyl quaternary compounds in alcohol and triethyl amine.

(iv) *Alpha, gamma* Diaza trimethin cyanines (both symmetrical and unsymmetrical, (I, X and Z = N and Y = CH) were prepared by refluxing the 2-amino quaternary salts with ethyl orthoformate in alcohol and triethylamine.

(v) Symmetrical mono aza pentamethin cyanines (X and Z = $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ and Y = N) were prepared by refluxing the acetanilido vinyl derivatives of different 2-methyl quaternary salts in alcoholic ammonia.

The absorption data of the aza cyanines have been compared with their corresponding carbon analogues (Table I and II). It was observed that a hypsochromic shift resulted, when $-\text{CH}=\text{}$ is replaced by $-\text{N}=\text{}$ in the chromophoric chain. These absorptions are quite consistent with the theoretical postulates of Forster and Knott.

In a dye of the above type when one $-\text{CH}=\text{}$ (II, X = CH) group in the chromophoric chain is replaced by $-\text{N}=\text{}$ (II, X = N) owing to the high electronegativity of nitrogen as compared to carbon, the replacement of $-\text{CH}-$ by $-\text{N}-$ will stabilise the inter auxochromic ionic excited structure and thus results in a hypsochromic shift. This has been studied by preparing a number of different types of aza cyanines. Thus the unsymmetrical cyanine

derived from acetanilido vinly derivative of 2-methyl benzothiazole methiodide with 2-methyl 4-phenyl thiazole methiodide absorbs at 560 $m\mu$ but the corresponding alpha aza, alpha- beta diaza and alpha- gamma diaza analogues absorbs at 450, 463 and 380 $m\mu$ respectively (Table I).

TABLE I

Nature of the nucleus 'A'	Nature of the nucleus 'B'	Absorption maxima in $m\mu$ Nature of XYZ				Hypsochromic shifts in $m\mu$		
		CH=CH -CH=	N=CH -CH=	N=N -CH=	N=CH -N=	a-b	a-c	a-d
		a	b	c	d			
Benzothiazole	Benzoxazole	520	450	—	—	70	—	—
-Do-	Benzothiazole	565	465	485	390	100	80	175
-Do-	alpha Naphtha thiazole	575	473	494	395	102	81	180
-Do-	beta Naphthathiazole	575	473	494	—	102	81	—
-Do-	4-Phenyl thiazole	560	450	463	380	110	97	180
-Do-	4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	580	—	475	385	—	105	195
-Do-	Quinoline-4	640	510	—	—	130	—	—
4-Phenylthiazole	Benzoxazole	520	450	—	—	70	—	—
-Do-	Benzothiazole	560	470	463	—	90	97	—
-Do-	alpha Naphtha thiazole	568	475	505	—	93	63	—
-Do-	beta Naphtha thiazole	568	475	505	—	93	63	—
-Do-	4-Phenyl thiazole	560	455	494	405	105	66	155
-Do-	4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	575	—	500	380	—	75	195
-Do-	Quinoline-4	640	500	—	—	140	—	—
4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	Benzoxazole	525	455	—	—	70	—	—
-Do-	Benzothiazole	580	485	510	—	95	70	—
-Do-	alpha Naphtha thiazole	590	495	530	—	95	60	—
-Do-	beta Naphtha thiazole	590	500	530	—	90	60	—
-Do-	4-Phenyl thiazole	575	465	495	—	100	80	—
-Do-	4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	585	—	500	375	—	85	215
-Do-	Lepidine	690	530	—	—	160	—	—
Beta Naphtha thiazole	Benzoxazole	525	465	—	—	60	—	—
-Do-	Benzothiazole	575	485	494	—	90	81	—
-Do-	4-Phenyl thiazole	575	468	482	—	107	93	—
Alpha Naphtha thiazole	Benzothiazole	575	470	—	—	105	—	—
-Do-	4-Phenyl thiazole	575	460	—	—	115	—	—

TABLE II

Nature of the nucleus 'A'	Nature of the nucleus 'B'	Absorption maxima in m μ Nature of X				Observed hypsochromic shift in m μ	
		CH	N	(-CH=)	(-CH=CH -N=CH -CH=)	a-b	c-d
		a	b	c	d		
Benzothiazole	Benzothiazole	425	400	665	555	25	110
4-Phenyl thiazole	4-Phenyl thiazole	420	390	660	555	30	105
alpha Naphtha thiazole	alpha Naphtha thiazole	440	410	690	575	30	115
beta Naphtha thiazole	beta Naphtha thiazole	440	410	690	580	30	110
Quinoline-4	Quinoline-4	—	—	810	655	—	155
4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	440	400	—	—	40	—
Benzothiazole	4-Phenyl thiazole	410	390	—	—	40	—
-Do-	4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	440	410	—	—	30	—
-Do-	alpha Naphtha thiazole	440	410	—	—	30	—
-Do-	beta Naphtha thiazole	440	410	—	—	30	—

From the magnitude of the deviation the relative basicities of various heterocyclic nuclei have been determined. As mentioned earlier, the hypsochromic shift resulting from the replacement of $-\text{CH} =$ by $-\text{N} =$ (II, a and b), is primarily caused by the resulting increased significance of the excited structure IIb. In order that the latter structure may contribute to the resonance hybrid, charge separation is required and the necessary energy required is offset by the gain in resonance energy of the molecule "B" by acquiring an additional double bond. Since the latter energy is a function of the electron repelling character of the nucleus it would be expected that the significance of the structure IIb and the hypsochromic shift resulting from the structural change would increase with the increasing electron repelling property ($-M$ effect) of the nucleus B. In the Table I it will be seen that the hypsochromic shift of alpha mono aza trimethin cyanine derived from benzoxazole and benzothiazole in 70 m μ , whereas the hypsochromic shift observed in the dye derived from quinoline-4 and benzothiazole is 130 m μ . In the light of above discussion it follows that quinoline-4 is more basic than benzoxazole. Similarly by varying the nucleus 'A', as well as 'B' and calculating the deviations it was observed (Table I, column 7) that the decreasing order of basicity follow the following sequence.

Quinoline-4 > 4-Phenyl thiazole > alpha and beta naphtha-thiazole > benzoxazole.

EXPERIMENTAL

(3-Methyl 4-Phenyl thiazole) (3-Methyl benzothiazole) alpha-beta diaza trimethin cyanine iodide : 2-(*p*-dimethylamine anilino methylene)-3-methyl benzo-thiazolium iodide (3.7 gm) was treated with 50% cold dilute hydrochloric acid (15 ml). N-methyl 4-phenyl triazole hydrazone (2 gm) was added portionwise to this solution with stirring. Then the whole

was boiled for three minutes and treated with a hot solution of KI (8 gm) in water (16 ml). The precipitated product was filtered off; washed first with water and then with ether. The residue was crystallised finally from hot methanol.

The analytical data, m.p. etc. of the related alpha beta diaza trimethin cyanines derived from N-methyl 4-phenyl thiazole hydrazone, N-methyl benzothiazole hydrazone, N-methyl 4,5 : diphenyl thiazole hydrazone and N-methyl beta naphtha-thiazole hydrazone with various heterocyclic nuclei are recorded in the Table III.

TABLE III

Alpha-beta diaza trimethin cyanines

Nature of the nucleus 'A'	Nature of the nucleus 'B'	Yield %	M.P. °C	λ_{max} in μ	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
Benzothiazole	Benzothiazole	65	225	485	43.69	43.77	3.18	3.21
-do-	alpha Naphtha thiazole	50	240	494	48.46	48.64	3.19	3.29
-do-	beta Naphtha thiazole	60	245	494	48.32	48.64	3.10	3.29
-do-	4-Phenyl thiazole	75	218	463	46.21	46.34	3.42	3.46
-do-	4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	75	210	475	52.76	52.82	3.62	3.69
4-Phenyl thiazole	Benzothiazole	85	238	463	46.18	46.34	3.40	3.46
-do-	alpha Naphtha thiazole	60	240	505	50.90	50.93	3.42	3.50
-do-	beta Naphtha thiazole	60	227	505	50.87	50.93	3.46	3.50
-do-	4-Phenyl thiazole	75	235	494	48.62	48.65	3.60	3.66
-do-	4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	75	222	500	54.48	54.54	3.82	3.87
4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	Benzothiazole	80	230	510	52.76	52.82	3.63	3.69
-do-	alpha Naphtha thiazole	65	150	530	56.18	56.31	3.65	3.72
-do-	beta Naphtha thiazole	65	170	530	56.20	56.31	3.69	3.72
-do-	4-Phenyl thiazole	70	140	495	54.42	54.54	3.79	3.87
-do-	4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	75	115	500	69.42	69.47	4.68	4.73
beta Naphtha thiazole	Benzothiazole	75	230	494	48.58	48.64	3.17	3.29
-do-	4-Phenyl thiazole	60	205	482	50.89	50.93	3.40	3.50

(3'-Methyl-2'-benzothiazole) (3-methyl 4-phenyl 2-thiazole) alpha aza trimethin cyanine iodide : 2-(2'-acetanilido vinyl) 3-methyl benzothiazolium iodide (0.35 gm) and 2-amino 4-phenyl thiazole methiodide (0.3 gm) were refluxed in absolute alcohol and triethylamine (1.2 drops) for ten minutes. The product obtained on cooling was crystallised from absolute alcohol.

The analytical data, m.p. etc. of the other aza methin cyanines derived from 2-amino 4-phenyl thiazole, 2-amino 4 : 5 : diphenyl thiazole, 2-amino benzothiazole, 2-amino alpha and beta naphtha-thiazole methiodides are recorded in the Table IV.

TABLE IV

Alpha mono aza trimethin cyanines

Nature of the nucleus 'A'	Nature of the nucleus 'B'	Yield %	M.P. °C	λ_{max} in m μ	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
Benzothiazole	Benzoxazole	50	213	450	48.01	48.11	3.47	3.56
-do-	Benzothiazole	75	245	465	46.38	46.70	3.40	3.44
-do-	alpha Naphtha thiazole	70	210	473	51.20	51.26	3.46	3.49
-do-	beta Naphtha thiazole	70	233	473	51.25	51.26	3.38	3.49
-do-	4-Phenyl thiazole	75	220	450	48.75	48.88	3.51	3.59
-do-	Quinoline-4	60	248	510	52.32	52.40	3.69	3.71
4-Phenyl thiazole	Benzoxazole	53	225	450	50.48	50.53	3.67	3.78
-do-	Benzothiazole	75	240	470	48.76	48.88	3.56	3.59
-do-	alpha Naphtha thiazole	65	224	475	53.12	53.23	3.65	3.69
-do-	beta Naphtha thiazole	65	248	475	53.10	53.23	3.60	3.69
-do-	4-Phenyl thiazole	70	198	455	50.91	51.06	3.81	3.86
-do-	Quinoline-4	63	205	500	53.21	53.27	4.18	4.22
4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	Benzoxazole	48	210	455	56.61	56.62	3.96	3.99
-do-	Benzothiazole	85	228	485	55.00	55.03	3.83	3.88
-do-	alpha Naphtha thiazole	70	200	495	57.47	57.54	3.80	3.89
-do-	beta Naphtha thiazole	75	198	500	57.42	57.54	3.81	3.89
-do-	4-Phenyl thiazole	80	215	465	56.63	56.65	4.00	4.04
-do-	Lepidine	73	815	530	59.82	59.88	4.23	4.27
beta Naphtha thiazole	Benzoxazole	39	212	465	52.03	52.07	3.00	3.09
-do-	Benzothiazole	85	215	485	51.18	51.26	3.45	3.49
-do-	4-Phenyl thiazole	85	240	468	53.19	53.23	3.63	3.69
alpha Naphtha thiazole	Benzothiazole	65	249	470	50.91	51.26	3.40	3.49
-do-	4-Phenyl thiazole	55	205	460	53.16	53.23	3.58	3.69

Bis-(3-methyl benzothiazole) 2-2'-diaz trimethin cyanine iodide: 2-Amino benzothiazole methiodide (2.8 gm) and ethyl ortho formate (2 ml) were refluxed in absolute alcohol (20 ml) with triethylamine (4 drops) for 30 min. It was cooled and the solid which separated was crystallised from ethanol.

The m.p. etc. of the other alpha-gamma diaza trimethin cyanines (both symmetrical and unsymmetrical) are given in the Table V.

TABLE V

Alpha-gamma diaza trimethin cyanines

Nature of the nucleus 'A'	Nature of the nucleus 'B'	Yield %	M.P. °C	λ_{max} in $m\mu$	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
Benzothiazole	Benzothiazole	45	150	390	43.72	43.77	3.16	3.21
-do-	4-Phenyl thiazole	50	250	380	56.28	46.34	3.39	3.45
-do-	4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	45	250	385	52.77	52.82	3.63	3.69
-do-	alpha Naphtha thiazole	42	250	395	48.80	48.84	3.22	3.29
-do-	beta Naphtha thiazole	48	250	395	—	—	—	—
4-Phenyl thiazole	4-Phenyl thiazole	43	200	405	48.61	48.65	3.60	3.66
4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	48	418	375	59.06	59.01	4.01	4.03
-do-	4-Phenyl thiazole	38	200	308	54.48	54.54	3.83	3.87

Bis (3-methyl benzothiazole) aza methin cyanine iodide : 2-Methyl mercapto benzothiazolium iodide (0.7 g.), 2-amino benzothiazole methiodide (0.6 g.) were refluxed in absolute alcohol (10 ml) with triethylamine (2 drops) for 10 minutes. The solid which separated was crystallised from ethanol.

The m.p. etc. of the related aza methin cyanines (both symmetrical and unsymmetrical) are given in the Table VI.

TABLE VI

Mono aza methin cyanines

Nature of the nucleus 'A'	Nature of the nucleus 'B'	Yield %	M.P. °C	λ_{max} in $m\mu$	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
Benzothiazole	Benzothiazole	36	210	400	43.42	43.73	3.10	3.19
-do-	4-Phenyl thiazole	40	168	390	46.28	46.34	3.39	3.45
-do-	4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	38	209	410	52.77	52.82	3.63	3.69
-do-	alpha Naphtha thiazole	35	220	410	48.80	48.84	3.22	3.29
-do-	beta Naphtha thiazole	35	250	410	48.79	48.84	3.27	3.29
4-Phenyl thiazole	4-Phenyl thiazole	35	187	309	48.61	48.65	3.60	3.66
4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	35	232	400	53.06	53.10	4.01	4.03
alpha Naphtha thiazole	alpha Naphtha thiazole	32	185	410	53.00	53.01	3.29	3.35
beta Naphtha thiazole	beta Naphtha thiazole	32	250	410	52.96	53.01	3.26	3.35

Bis-(3-methyl benzothiazole) mono aza pentamethin cyanine iodide : 2-(2'-acetanilido vinyl) 3-methyl benzothiazolium iodide (0.7 gm) was dissolved in alcohol saturated with ammonia. It was refluxed for 2 hrs and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The product obtained was crystallised from methanol.

The m.p. etc. of the different mono aza pentamethin cyanines derived from various heterocyclic nuclei are recorded in the Table VII.

TABLE VII

Mono aza pentamethin cyanines

Nature of the nuclears 'A'	Yield %	M.P. °C	λ_{max} in $m\mu$	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
Benzothiazole	35	165	555	48.87	48.89	3.56	3.66
4-Phenyl thiazole	30	230	555	52.92	53.13	4.01	4.05
alpha Naphtha thiazole	28	250	575	56.64	56.84	3.68	3.72
beta Naphtha thiazole	30	250	580	56.75	56.84	3.62	3.72
Lepidine	37	201	655	50.29	60.38	4.02	4.19

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